

Organic macromolecules and Ca-phosphate components in Cambrian small shelly fossils: characterization and diagenesis

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Summary

There are few studies using the synchronous analysis of organophosphatic small shelly fossils (SSFs), despite their potential importance for understanding the Cambrian explosion. The nature of organic biopolymers in the shells of many SSFs is still unknown. Here, shell matrices in SSFs within lower Cambrian carbonate strata across the Arrowie Basin in South Australia were characterized. The findings were compared with the SSFs from other localities in Europe. This work provides excellent potential for large-scale screening of fossilised organic remains in biominerals.

Abstract

Thousands of small shelly fossils (SSFs) occur within lower Cambrian carbonate strata across the Arrowie Basin in South Australia (Betts et al. 2016, 2017, Larsson et al. 2014). However, there are few studies using the synchronous analysis to interpret the organic-inorganic hybrid component of these organophosphatic biominerals, despite their potential importance for understanding the Cambrian explosion. The nature of organic biopolymers in the shells of many SSFs is still unknown. Here, sclerites from the tannuolinid tommotiid *Micrina etheridgei*, the camenellan tommotiid *Dailyatia macroptera*, and one of the oldest known brachiopods from East Gondwana, *Askepasma toddense*, have been studied using micro-Raman spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), field-emission-gun and Phenol XL desktop scanning electron microscopes. These SSF taxa are palaeontologically important since they represent basal lophotrochozoan marine invertebrates and, because they secrete diagenetically stable, well preserved and readily identifiable biominerals. This study reveals for the first time the inorganic-organic hybrid composite components of these organophosphatic samples. FTIR spectra show the characteristic infrared absorption peaks for the amide I and III moieties of collagen matrix and/or glycosaminoglycan, comparable to the organic components of recently-alive (modern) linguliform brachiopod shells. A $\sim 1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peak from Raman spectra is assigned to proteoglycan, although the peak overlaps with the collagen matrix and components of phosphate groups. A Raman peak at $\sim 1003\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to phenylalanine and thus overlaps with the HPO_4^{2-} ion. Energy disperse X-ray spectra show a sulphur peak, which is attributed to the presence of proteoglycan, a glycosaminoglycan associated with a core protein. Shell matrices of the described assemblages are also compared with the SSFs from other localities in Europe such as Sweden, France, and Belgium. This work provides excellent potential for large-scale screening of fossilised organic remains that are important sources of biological and evolutionary information with long-term potential for phylogenetic exploration.

References

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